

ACTION OF *p*-TOLUENE SULPHONYL CHLORIDE ON NITROPHENOLS

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The action of *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride on a number of substituted nitronaphthols, nitro-cresols, dinitrodihydroxydiphenyl and 1:2-dihydroxyanthraquinone has been studied. Condensation either in the presence of diethylaniline or sodium carbonate results in the formation of a *p*-toluene sulphonyl ester, in every case. 1:2-Dihydroxyanthraquinone although containing two hydroxy groups yields only a monotosyl sulphonyl derivative; the inactivity of one of the hydroxyl groups (occupying position 1) has been attributed to the presence of two *ortho* substituents. The reactivity of these esters with aniline has also been studied.

Nitrophenols react with *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride in two ways: (1) Mononitrophenols yield *p*-toluene sulphonyl esters in the presence of sodium carbonate or diethylaniline as the condensing agent; (2) poly-nitrophenols, having nitro groups in 2:4 or 2:6 positions also yield such esters in the presence of sodium carbonate as the condensing agent but are converted mainly into poly-nitrochlorobenzenes in the presence of diethylaniline (Ullmann and Nadai, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 1870; Ullmann and Brück, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 3939; Ullmann and Sane, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 3730; Sane and Joshi, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 2481; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 59; 1933, 10, 313, 459; Sane, Chakravarty and Pramanick, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 55).

In the present paper this reaction has been extended to 1:6-dinitro- β -naphthol, 4-nitro- α -naphthol, 1-nitro-6-bromo- β -naphthol, 1:3:6-tribromo- β -naphthol, 5:5'-dinitro-2:2'-dihydroxydiphenylmethane, 2-nitroresorcinol, 2-nitro-*p*-cresol, 2-nitro-6-bromo-*p*-cresol and 1:2-dihydroxyanthraquinone, with a view to studying the replacibility of the hydroxyl groups, specially in the presence of NO₂ and Br groups, when they are present in positions other than 2:4 or 2:6 or in different nuclei. In every case a *p*-toluene sulphonyl ester is obtained, either in the presence of sodium carbonate or diethylaniline, showing thereby that these groups have little or no effect when they are present in positions other than 2:4 or 2:6. However, a marked difference in the reactivity of these compounds towards aniline is brought about by the presence of these groups. It is observed that only those tosyl derivatives of naphthol, which contained a NO₂ group in the *ortho* position to the OH and another NO₂ or Br (acid) group in the second benzene ring, react easily with aniline; others without such a grouping fail to give this reaction—thus the tosyl derivatives of 4-nitro- α -naphthol and 1:3:6-tribromo- β -naphthol could not be made to condense with aniline. It may be recalled that the behaviour of these compounds in this respect is similar to the behaviour of the tosyl derivatives of azonitrophenols observed by the author previously (*Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1937, 7, 218); 1:2-dihydroxyanthraquinone although containing two OH groups yields only a monotosyl derivative. This compound has been assigned the constitution 1-oxy 2-tosyl-anthraquinone, as it is believed that the OH group in position 1 is unable to react due to steric hindrance.

TABLE I

Nitrophenol used.	Wt. of Nitro-phenol.	Wt. of <i>p</i> toluene sulphonyl chloride.	Yield of tosyl ester using		M. p.	Formulae of Tosyl ester.	Analysis		Reactivity with aniline.	M. p.	N in the amide.	
			Diethyl aniline.	Sodium carbonate.			(%)	(%)			Found.	Calc.
(1) 1:6-Dinitro- β -naphthol	2.3 g.	2.0 g.	3.0 g.	3.2 g.	181°	$C_{17}H_{13}O_2NS$	8.1%	8.2%	Reactive	195°	13.3%	13.6%
(2) 4-Nitro- α -naphthol	2.2	2.0 g.	2.9	3.3	138°	$C_{17}H_{13}O_2NS$	9.5	9.3	Not reactive	—	—	—
(3) 1-Nitro-6-bromo- β naphthol	2.7	2.0 g.	4.2	3.8	145°	$C_{17}H_{11}O_4NBrS$	7.3	7.6	Reactive	156°	8.1	8.1
(4) 1:3:6-Tri-bromo- β naphthol	3.8	2.0 g.	2.6	4.8	150°	$C_{17}H_{11}O_3BrS$	5.94	6.0	Not reactive	—	—	—
(5) 5:5-Dinitro-2:2-dihydroxy-diphenyl-methane	1.5	2.0 g.	2.7	2.6	155°	$C_{20}H_{12}O_{10}N_2S_2$	10.54	10.7	—	—	—	—
(6) 2-Nitroresorcinol	1.6	2.0 g.	3.7	3.5	140°	$C_{10}H_7O_4NS_2$	13.68	13.8	—	—	—	—
(7) 2-Nitro-4-methylphenol	3.0	4.0 g.	5.4	5.2	91°	$C_{11}H_{13}NO_3S$	10.6	10.4	—	—	—	—
(8) 2-Nitro-4-methyl-6-bromophenol	2.3	2.0 g.	2.1	2.4	128°	$C_{11}H_{11}O_4NBrS$	8.03	8.3	—	—	—	—
(9) 1:2-Dihydroxyanthraquinone	2.4	4.0 g.	3.4	3.2	211°	$C_{14}H_9O_6S$	7.9	8.1	—	—	—	—

EXPERIMENTAL

The toluene sulphonyl (tosyl) esters of the nitrophenols were obtained by condensing the appropriate nitrophenol with *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride either in the presence of sodium carbonate or diethylaniline. The exact method followed in the case of 1 : 6-dinitro- β naphthol is given below.

1 : 6-Dinitronaphthalene-2-toluene sulphonyl ester : (a) *Condensation in the presence of sodium carbonate.*—1 : 6-Dinitro- β -naphthol (2.3 g.) and *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride (2 g.) were suspended in 20 c.c. of boiling water, contained in a flask. Solid sodium carbonate was then added to it little by little. Each addition produced a coloration which disappeared on heating. The addition of sodium carbonate was stopped when further addition failed to produce such coloration. The contents of the flask were then cooled, the solid matter which separated out was washed thoroughly with water and then filtered, dried and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 181°, yield 3. g.

(b) *Condensation in the presence of diethylaniline.*—1 : 6-Dinitro- β -naphthol (2.3 g.), *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride (2 g.) and diethylaniline (10 c.c.) were heated on the water-bath for 4 hours. After cooling, the diethylaniline was decomposed with dilute hydrochloric acid when a solid mass separated out. This was washed with hot water several times, filtered and finally recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 181°, yield 3.2 g. (Found : S, 8.1. $C_{17}H_{12}O_7N_2S$ requires S, 8.2 per cent).

The other nitrophenols were condensed with *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride by following the same method. The results obtained are given in Table I.

1 : 6-Dinitronaphthalene-2-phenylamine.—The *p*-toluene sulphonyl ester of 1 : 6-dinitronaphthol (1 g.) was refluxed with 5 c.c. of freshly distilled aniline for about 15 minutes. The excess of aniline was removed with hydrochloric acid, after cooling the contents of the flask. A yellow solid compound separated out. This was repeatedly washed with hot water, filtered, dried and finally recrystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 195°, yield 0.7 g. (Found : N, 13.3. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 13.6 per cent).

1-Nitro-6-bromonaphthalene-2-phenylamine was obtained as before by refluxing the tosyl derivative of 1-nitro-6-bromo- β -naphthol (1 g.) with 5 c.c. of freshly distilled aniline, m.p. 156°, yield 0.6 g. (Found : N, 8.1. $C_{16}H_{11}O_2N_2Br$ requires N, 8.1 per cent).

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